

IMPROVEMENTS OF YOUNG'S MODULUS ON NI-BASED CNT COMPOSITE COATING

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1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) as reinforcements for metallic, ceramic and polymer composites due to their high Young's modulus [1,2]. Recent experiments have shown the Young's modulus of carbon nanotube to be between 300 to 1500 GPa [1,2]. The high strength is a result of the near perfect structure and the strong sp² bonding between the C-C bonds. Research on metal matrix composites has been increasing. Metal matrix CNT composites have a great potential in load bearing applications and electronic packaging due to their high strength and high thermal conductivity.

Metal matrix CNT composites have been fabricated by powder metallurgy techniques, melt processing, electrochemical techniques, and other novel techniques. Electrochemical techniques are useful for partially improvement of the surface property. Some recent researches have reported that friction and wear properties of Ni-based CNT composite coatings are improved by codepositing CNTs in the matrix [3]. We had also investigated the improvement in the tool life of electroplated diamond tools by Ni-based CNT composite coatings [4] and in wear resistance of electrical discharge machining electrodes by Cu-based CNT composite coatings [5, 6]. In this study, furthermore, effects of

CNT composites on Young's modulus of Ni-based CNT composite coating were investigated by using indentation method. Especially, the mechanical properties of the coating which have high CNT concentration layers were evaluated by experiments and numerical calculations.

2 Experimental Procedures

Table 1 lists the plating bath composition and operation conditions for Ni-based CNT composite coatings. Ni-based CNT composite coatings were deposited on tungsten carbide substrates by electroplating using a nickel sulphamate plating bath adding 1 – 10 g/l CNTs under galvanostatic conditions. CNTs used in this study were multi-walled carbon nanotubes (NC7000, Nanocyl) and were typically 9.5 nm in average diameter and 1.5 μm in average length. Substrates were tungsten carbide as anodes. A pure Ni plate was used as the cathode. The plating bath was controlled at 45 °C. Ultrasonic vibration (24kHz, 150W) was radiated to the plating bath by Horn sonication method during electroplating in order to improve CNTs dispersion. For DC electroplating, current density was controlled at 5 A/dm² by a galvanostat. For PR electroplating, the conditions

Table 1 The electroplating bath composition and the operating conditions

Bath	Ni(NH ₂ SO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O: 500 g/L, NiCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O: 4 g/L, H ₃ BO ₃ : 33 g/L
Agitation	Horn sonication
Bath temperature	45 °C
Current density	DC: I _{ON} = -5 [A/dm ²] PR: I _{ON} /I _{REV} = -1/6 [A/dm ²], T _{ON} /T _{REV} = 3.6/0.4 [sec], 250mHz
Process time	DC: 60 min, PR: 240 min
Substrate	Micro fine grade cemented carbide (HTi10, Mitsubishi Materials Corporation: cobalt content : 6 mass%, grain size < 1.0μm)

were as follows; frequency: 250mHz, Duty: anodic time T_{ON} / cathodic time $T_{REV} = 9/1$, anodic current I_{ON} : -1 A/dm^2 , cathodic current I_{REV} : 6 A/dm^2 .

For characterization of hardness and Young's modulus of the coatings, Load-displacement curves for the coatings were measured by a dynamic hardness tester (DUH-200, Shimadzu, Japan). The condition for the measurement were as follows; Maximum load: 98mN, load speed: 2.65mN/sec, keeping time: 5sec, probe tip: Berkovich 115-deg diamond-tip. Dynamic hardness of the coatings was calculated by maximum load P_{MAX} [mN] and maximum displacement d_{MAX} [μm] using the following equation;

$$DH = 3.8584 \frac{P_{MAX}}{d_{MAX}^2} \quad (1)$$

Young's modulus of the coatings was calculated by slopes of unload-displacement curve at unloading rate 0 – 30%.

The surface chemical composition was determined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using monochromatic Al K α radiation.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Volume fraction of CNTs in Ni-based CNT composite coatings

Figure 1 shows the SEM image of surface of a Ni-based CNT composite coating formed by PR electroplating. A lot of CNTs embedded in Ni matrix can be observed in this figure. Most of Ni crystalline is tens of nm in diameter and Ni crystalline size decreased by containing CNTs.

Figure 2 shows XPS depth profiles of C1s for the CNT composite coatings. Volume fraction of the carbon indicates almost that of carbon nanotubes. The depth is calculated by Ar sputtering time and sputtering rates for each element, carbon and nickel. Volume fraction of CNTs in PR electroplatings is much higher than that in DC electroplatings. Both of DC and PR electroplatings have high concentration CNT composite layer at the surface, in 1–2 μm

3.2 Dynamic hardness and Young's modulus

Figure 3 shows the typical load-displacement curves of the coatings. Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the dynamic hardness and Young's modulus, respectively, plotted against amount of CNTs in a plating bath. Each experiment was repeated at

Fig. 1 SEM image of Ni-based CNT composite coating formed by PR electroplating

Fig.2 XPS depth profiles of C1s for the CNT composite coatings (DC 1g/L, PR 1g/L)

least five times. The error bars here represent standard deviations. Dynamic hardness of DC coatings, which are formed by DC electroplating, increases rapidly up to 2g/L, above which it decreases gradually. The dynamic hardness of DC coating at 2g/L is 571 DH_{115} and almost three times as hard as that of pure Ni coating. Young's modulus of DC coatings also increases up to 1–2g/L, above which it decreases gradually. From these results it can be stated that DC coating has the highest dynamic hardness and highest Young's modulus at 1–2g/L CNTs.

Dynamic hardness of PR coating, which is formed by PR electroplating is lower than that of DC coating at 1g/L CNTs. On the other hand, Young's

modulus of PR coating is higher than that of DC coating at 1g/L CNTs. The slope of load-displacement curve in PR coating at low load range is much gentler than that at high load range, shown as Fig. 3. This result indicates that the soft layer existed at PR coating surface. Figure 4 shows XPS depth profiles of C1s for DC coating and PR coating electrodeposited by the bath adding 1g/L CNTs. Carbon composition of PR coating is much higher than that of DC coating at surface. This result indicates that CNTs are rich at the surface, especially for PR coating. The CNT concentration at the surface was so high that the porous structured layer was formed at the surface and dynamic hardness was decreased due to the soft porous layer with a lot of CNTs. The soft layer didn't have great influence on Young's modulus measurements because Young's modulus was calculated by the slope of load-displacement curves at high load range. High Young's modulus of PR coatings is considered to be due to high CNT concentration which was increased by measurement load.

3.3 Numerical calculation of Young's modulus by Halpin-Tsai equations

The Young's modulus of particulate reinforced composites can be predicted from the Halpin-Tsai equations [7,8] which are represented by

$$E_C = \frac{E_{Ni}(1 + \eta q V_{CNT})}{1 - q V_{CNT}} \quad (2)$$

$$q = \frac{E_{CNT}/E_{Ni} - 1}{E_{CNT}/E_{Ni} + \eta} \quad (3)$$

where E_C , E_{Ni} , E_{CNT} are the Young's modulus of the composite, Ni matrix, and CNTs, respectively, η is an adjustable parameter, and V_{CNT} is the volume fraction of CNTs. For Ni-based CNT composites, $E_{Ni} = 125\text{--}175$ GPa measured values, and $E_{CNT} = 1200$ GPa.

Most CNTs lie on the surface and are embedded in coatings as shown in Fig. 1 so that Young's modulus is calculated by taking $\eta = 2$ [7, 8]. Figure 6 show Young's moduli of the coatings calculated by Halpin-Tsai equations. The measured Young's moduli of Ni-based CNT composites formed by DC-coating, which is low CNT volume

Fig. 3 Load–displacement curves for the coatings measured by indentations

Fig.4 Dynamic Hardness of the coatings plotted as a function of amount of CNTs in a plating bath.

Fig.5 Young's Modulus of the coatings plotted as a function of amount of CNTs in a plating bath.

Fig. 6 Young's modulus of Ni-based composite coating calculated and measured.

fraction, is higher than the calculated value. This is probably due to decreasing Ni crystalline size by containing CNTs. On the other hand, The measured Young's moduli of Ni-based CNT composites formed by PR-coating, which is high CNT volume fraction, agree well with the predictions of Halpin-Tsai equation as shown in Fig. 6.

Some researchers had explored that at high concentrations (> 2 vol.%), poor dispersion of the CNTs has an affect of reducing the strengthening. However, at high concentrations in the PR coating, measured Young's moduli exceptionally agree with the calculated value. This result indicate that CNTs are well dispersed in PR coating which has high CNT concentration

4 Conclusion

The following conclusions were derived from the results and discussion.

1. Young's modulus of Ni electroplated coating is increased by containing CNTs.
2. Ni-based CNT composite coatings with high CNT concentration layer at surface have a higher Young's modulus.
3. The measured Young's moduli agree well with the predictions of Halpin-Tsai equations at high CNT concentration.

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